

Sets of Objects: An Ontology of Physical Reality

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Abstract

This paper presents an ontological approach to physical reality, based on the notion of sets of similar objects, in which an object appears not as a single isolated entity but as a class of realisations of a certain type that is continually created by the set itself.

The properties of objects are examined, and a criterion of ontological existence is formulated, based on belonging to a set of objects that creates new objects of its own type.

It is shown how the proposed ontology leads to a description of the motion of massless and massive objects as wave processes. Consistency with special relativity and the structure of Minkowski spacetime is demonstrated; the photon and the massive process receive an ontological interpretation through light-like components.

The set of basic objects is interpreted as a homogeneous, isotropic physical medium.

The approach does not alter the mathematical formalism of contemporary physics, but offers its ontological interpretation.

Ключові слова / Keywords: ontology of physical reality; sets of objects; phase invariance; Minkowski spacetime; entropy; physical field; philosophy of physics

Introduction

Modern physics has produced an exceptionally successful mathematical description of nature, encompassing classical mechanics, quantum field theory, thermodynamics, and the special and general theories of relativity. Within these theories, the fundamental concepts of spacetime, physical vacuum, matter, field, physical system, motion, and entropy are used.

At the same time, the mathematical description of physical processes does not always determine the ontological status of the physical entities themselves. Particles may be described as excitations of fields, the vacuum as the lowest energy state, and motion as a change of states of physical systems in spacetime. The question of what, among these entities, is a physically existing object and what is a structure or a way of description remains open in the philosophy of physics.

This work proposes an ontological approach based on the concept of pluralities of objects and on the criterion of the existence of objects through the capacity of their set to create new objects of its own type. Within this approach, a distinction is drawn between objects and structures that arise from the interaction of objects.

The aim of this work is to examine what conceptual consequences follow from the proposed approach and to what extent they agree with existing physical knowledge. On this basis, the physical vacuum, the wave nature of motion, and localized physical structures are considered in connection with special relativity. The proposed approach does not change the mathematical formalisms of modern physics and does not claim to revise its established ontology; if it proves conceptually fruitful, it may serve as a complementary interpretational framework for the analysis of physical reality.

1 Contemporary Academic and Conceptual Approaches to the Ontology of Physical Reality

This section examines how modern physics and the philosophy of physics treat fundamental concepts of physical reality.

The aim of this section is to outline the contemporary academic framework within which physical and philosophical conceptions of reality are formed.

Modern physics employs complex mathematical formalisms to describe physical phenomena. The development of these formalisms is accompanied by the formation of ontological conceptions of the nature of physical reality. Such conceptions play an important role in shaping physical intuitions, interpretations, and conceptual models that accompany the development of physical theories.

At the same time, the philosophy of physics addresses the ontological status of such concepts, the relationship between mathematical description and physical reality, and the question of which entities may be regarded as fundamental elements of the physical world.

1.1 Ontological Concepts in Physical Science

In modern physics, fundamental conceptions of physical reality are described within different theoretical approaches and mathematical formalisms. Despite differences among individual theories, there exists a certain system of basic ontological concepts used to describe physical reality.

Such concepts include, among others, material bodies, elementary particles, classical and quantum fields, vacuum, space, spacetime, interactions, physical systems, and physical states.

In the following items, we briefly consider how these concepts are defined and interpreted in modern physics.

1.1.1 Spacetime as the Basis of Physical Description

In modern physics, physical processes are described within spacetime — a geometric continuum which in special relativity is

given by Minkowski space. In Einstein's general theory of relativity, spacetime may be curved, and its geometry is linked to the distribution of energy and momentum through the equations of the gravitational field (Landau and Lifshitz 1975; Carroll 2019).

In the physical description, spacetime:

- provides the geometric structure for the description of physical processes;
- is used for the coordinate description of physical states and processes;
- is not identified with matter and is not regarded as a collection of localized material objects;
- is not identified with physical fields, which are themselves defined on spacetime;
- is not identified with the physical vacuum.

Thus, spacetime serves as a universal geometric continuum within which the basic physical concepts are defined and physical theories are formulated, while its geometry is determined by the distribution of matter, energy, and momentum.

1.1.2 Physical Vacuum as a State of Space Without Matter

At all levels of modern physical description, vacuum is defined through the absence of matter:

- in classical physics — as a region of space without material bodies;
- in special relativity — as space without material particles, in which classical fields may exist;
- in general relativity — as a region in which the energy-momentum tensor equals zero (Landau and Lifshitz 1975; Carroll 2019);
- in quantum field theory — as the lowest energy state of the field system, in which particles are absent (Weinberg 1995).

In quantum field theory, the concept of vacuum is refined through vacuum fluctuations and non-zero properties of field operators. At the same time, such states:

- do not form stable particles;
- are not regarded as matter;
- are not described as a material medium.

Thus, in modern physics the physical vacuum is regarded as a state of spacetime in which matter is absent, even if quantum fields have non-zero vacuum properties.

1.1.3 Matter as Localized Structures with Mass

In classical physics, matter consists of bodies that have mass, volume, and the ability to interact. In quantum mechanics, matter is described through particles with certain quantum numbers.

In quantum field theory (Weinberg 1995):

- matter is described as stable localized excitations of fermionic fields;
- particles have mass, charge, spin, and other quantum numbers;
- matter differs from physical fields by its localization and the presence of stable quantum characteristics.

Richard Feynman formulates this most clearly:

“Matter consists of fermions. Everything else — is not matter.” (Feynman, Leighton, and Sands 1965)

Thus, in modern physics matter is regarded as a collection of localized stable structures that possess mass, quantum numbers, and the capacity for physical interactions.

1.1.4 Field as a Form of Description of Physical Interactions

In classical electrodynamics, a field is described as a distribution of physical quantities in spacetime that determine the interaction between particles (Jackson 1999).

In the physical description, a field:

- is not regarded as a material body;
- is not described as a localized material object;
- is used to describe interactions and the transfer of physical influences.

In quantum field theory, a field is regarded as a fundamental element of the physical formalism, and particles are described as excitations of the corresponding quantum fields (Weinberg 1995).

Richard Feynman formulated this as follows:

“A field is not a thing; it is a way of describing how one particle affects another.” (Feynman, Leighton, and Sands 1965)

Max Born generalized:

“The electromagnetic field is not a substance. A field is a state of space.” (Born 1949)

Thus, in modern physics a field is regarded as a form of description of physical interactions and states in spacetime, but is not directly identified with matter.

1.1.5 Physical System

In modern physics, an important role is played by the representation of physical processes through the concept of a physical system. Physical objects, fields, particles, and their interactions are regarded as systems or parts of systems whose state may change over time.

In classical mechanics, thermodynamics, quantum mechanics, and quantum field theory, the physical system is used as the basic unit of physical description. A system is defined through:

- a set of elements or degrees of freedom;
- interactions between them;
- possible states and their evolution in time.

In the Lagrangian and Hamiltonian formalisms, physical processes are described through the dynamics of systems and the change of their states.

Thus, in modern physics the typical form of describing physical processes is to represent them as physical systems described in spacetime through the interaction of material objects, fields, energy, and potentials.

1.1.6 Motion as a Change of State of a Physical System

In modern physics, motion is regarded as a change of the state of a physical system in time.

In classical mechanics, motion is described through the change of the coordinates of bodies in spacetime, as well as through the change of the configuration of a physical system and the relative arrangement of its elements.

In modern physical theories, the concept of motion is generalized and includes:

- the evolution of physical systems;
- the change of states of fields;
- wave processes;
- quantum dynamics;
- thermodynamic processes.

In the Lagrangian and Hamiltonian formalisms, motion is defined through the evolution of dynamical variables and states of a physical system in time.

Thus, in modern physics motion is regarded as a universal form of change of physical systems and their states in spacetime.

1.1.7 Entropy as a Measure of States of a Physical System

In modern physics, entropy is a fundamental characteristic of physical systems, associated with the number of possible microstates corresponding to a given macroscopic state of the system.

In classical thermodynamics, entropy is used to describe the irreversibility of physical processes and the direction of evolution of systems.

In statistical physics, entropy is defined through the number of possible microstates of the system and the degree of statistical uncertainty of its state (Landau and Lifshitz 1980).

In quantum mechanics and quantum field theory, entropy is also used to describe quantum states, informational properties of systems, and their evolution.

Thus, in modern physics entropy is regarded as a fundamental characteristic of the state of a physical system, reflecting its statistical structure and possible forms of evolution.

1.2 Main Directions of Contemporary Scientific Realism in the Interpretation of Fundamental Physical Theories

The ontological interpretation of fundamental physical theories in contemporary philosophy of science is carried out within several influential directions of scientific realism. These approaches differ from one another in which elements of scientific theories are regarded as ontologically significant, but all of them proceed from the assumption of the objective reality of the physical world.

The classical antecedents of the modern structural and realist positions were formulated in the works of Henri Poincaré (Poincaré 1902) and Bertrand Russell (Russell 1927). Poincaré emphasised the conventional character of physical descriptions and the primary role of experimentally testable relations over a priori ontological assumptions about the nature of the entities described. Russell regarded matter not as a substance but as a structure of events, and physical objects as logical constructions out of sets of relations between them. These positions underlie many of the directions surveyed below and are directly consonant with the ontology developed in the

present work.

Scientific Realism

In its general form, scientific realism asserts that successful physical theories describe real aspects of the world, and that their theoretical entities have ontological status. Classical formulations of this approach are associated with the names of Hilary Putnam and Richard Boyd.

Object (substantial) realism

Within this approach, fundamental physical entities are treated as objects or as carriers of properties. The theoretical elements of physics — particles, fields, bodies — are regarded as really existing objects, independent of the ways in which they are described. This position is historically associated with the classical forms of scientific realism and remains widespread in philosophical interpretations of physics.

Epistemic structural realism

This direction, proposed by John Worrall, emphasizes that when scientific theories change, what is preserved above all are mathematical and nomological structures, whereas the ontological status of objects remains an open question.

Ontic Structural Realism

In this approach, structure is regarded as ontologically primary, and physical objects — as derived elements or stabilized configurations of structural relations. This position is most systematically presented in the works of James Ladyman and Steven French.

Moderate realist approaches

Alongside the radical structural versions, there exist positions that combine recognition of the ontological significance of structures with the preservation of the realist status of objects. Such approaches are represented, in particular, in the works of Stathis Psillos.

The systems approach

The systems approach regards nature as a hierarchy of inter-related systems of various levels of organisation, each with its own structural and dynamical properties. This direction is represented, in particular, in the works of the Ukrainian scientist Vladimir Vernadsky (Vernadsky 1926; Vernadsky 1945), who considered living and non-living matter within a single ontological framework — as different levels of organisation of one physical medium; an important notion of his approach is that of “living

matter” as a planetary factor.

The directions outlined form the contemporary philosophical field within which the interpretation of fundamental physical theories and their ontological presuppositions is carried out. The further exposition of this work develops with regard to this spectrum of positions, without prior commitment to any of them as methodologically binding.

1.3 General Conclusion of Section 1

Modern physics regards the concepts of space (spacetime), vacuum, field, and matter as fundamental but ontologically heterogeneous components of physical reality. Within established mathematical formalisms, these concepts are clearly distinguished and perform defined operational functions: spacetime provides the geometric structure, vacuum is defined as a state without matter, field describes interactions, and matter is identified with stable localized objects.

At the same time, analysis of academic definitions and the views of leading physicists shows that such a distinction does not exhaust the ontological content of the corresponding concepts. Even within formally correct and empirically successful theories, vacuum does not appear as simple emptiness, field is not reduced to a purely mathematical tool, and matter is not exhausted by a set of isolated objects. This indicates the presence of a deeper conceptual tension between the formal description of physical theories and their ontological interpretation.

Thus, the modern physical description of reality turns out to be methodologically effective but ontologically fragmented: different types of physical entities are introduced as fundamentally distinct, without an explicit common foundation.

2 Ontology of Sets of Objects

In this case, ontology means the investigation of what objects are in themselves, rather than of the ways they are described, measured, classified, or mathematically formalized.

The central question is the criterion for the existence of objects independently of observation, experiment, or the manner

in which they are singled out.

The propositions formulated below are not introduced as axioms, but as an ontological interpretation of regularities observed in physical reality.

The general scheme of the investigation is as follows:

1. consider the regularities observed in physical reality, including experimental data, physical laws, and stable forms of organization;
2. separate physical reality from the ways it is described and from mathematical models;
3. formulate ontological properties of objects that are consistent with such regularities.

Why Sets of Objects

In physical reality we observe not isolated entities, but sets of similar entities that arise, exist, and cease to exist according to common regularities.

Such similar entities can be formed in two fundamentally different ways:

- through the creation of similar objects by the set;
- through assembly or self-organization from similar components, symmetrical conditions, or similar physical processes.

These two ways give rise to ontologically different types of formations and therefore require a principled distinction.

Object Creation

In this work, **object creation** is understood as a property of a set of objects: such a set creates new objects of its own type on the basis of objects of this set that already exist. This property is also referred to as *replication* in other contexts.

Objects and Structures

Henceforth, sets of similar entities that are formed through such creation by the set will be called **sets of objects**, and their elements—**objects**.

Such objects include ontological entities that correspond to scientific concepts of elementary particles, atoms, cells, and organisms.

Alongside sets of objects, we observe sets of other similar formations. For example, snowflakes form large sets of nearly identical individual forms; however, such repetition alone does not imply that they are objects in the sense defined above.

In these cases, we are dealing with **structures** that arise as a result of interaction among objects, and their similarity is determined by the properties of these objects and by similar physical processes of their interaction.

Such formations are physically real, may have synergetic properties, but do not themselves create new objects of their own type and therefore do not form sets of objects.

Criterion for the Existence of Objects

Henceforth, existence in an ontological sense is considered primarily as a property of objects and their sets.

This distinction does not mean that such physical formations as snowflakes or matter are not physically real. They exist, yet not as objects in the sense defined above, but as structures formed by the sets of objects of which they are composed.

Thus, the ontological status of an object is determined by its belonging to a set of objects and by the capacity of this set to create new objects of its own type. This property alone secures the ontological difference between an object and other physical formations.

By contrast, a structure may repeat, yet its existence is determined not by the creative process of its own set, but by the configuration and interaction of the objects from which it is formed.

Having made these preliminary remarks, we next consider the properties of sets of objects and structures in the form of ontological propositions.

2.1 Properties of Objects

Within the proposed ontology of sets of objects, the following properties of objects can be formulated.

Multiplicity, Criterion of Existence.

Only sets of similar objects exist.

Emergence, Object Creation.

Each object arises through object creation by its set.

This means that the structure of an object and the processes by which the set creates new objects are internal properties of

the corresponding set of objects.

Variability.

Objects belonging to the same set of objects may differ in physical states, parameters, or the character of their interactions.

Time of Existence and Motion.

Each object goes through a sequence of emergence, existence, object creation by the set, and cessation of existence.

This sequence is a physical process that defines motion in the fundamental sense as the preservation and transmission of the object's structure. Within such an approach, time may be regarded as an internal characteristic of the corresponding set of objects, given by the duration of realization of these processes.

Organization and Hierarchy.

Each object:

- is realized as a locally organized structure of interacting objects of the previous level;
- has internal organization necessary for preserving its stability;
- interacts with surrounding objects and structures.

Sets of similar objects:

- can form collective structures as a result of coordinated organization of objects of this set;
- under appropriate conditions can generate sets of objects of the next level of organization.

Interaction of Levels and Dynamics of the Set.

The existence and dynamics of a set of objects are determined by the relationship between objects of a given level of organization and objects of the previous level with which they interact.

Changes in this relationship lead to changes in the number and states of objects of the corresponding set.

Typical dynamic regimes:

- predominance of objects of a previous level → growth of the set;
- limited availability of objects of a previous level → decrease of the set;
- relative equilibrium between levels → small oscillations of number and states.

Emergence of Sets of Objects.

Objects are complex structures that have their own processes of stabilization and object creation, and do not arise as random combinations of objects of the previous level.

In general, the appearance of new types of objects is a consequence of the development of structures of previous levels of matter organization and reflects evolutionary processes in the Universe. This proposition is consistent with modern cosmological and evolutionary theories and logically follows from the above properties of objects.

2.2 Structures Formed from Objects

Since objects are represented by sets, these sets can form structures. Such structures are a necessary way of organizing objects in the physical environment and determine the conditions of their existence, interaction, and stability.

At the macroscopic level, such structures include matter, solids, liquids, gases, chemical compounds, and so on. Such formations may include objects of different types and of different hierarchical levels.

These structures form the environment in which objects exist and interact, but are not themselves objects in the ontological sense used in this work. At the same time, a stabilized structure, realized within an individual object, determines its internal organization.

2.3 Implications of the Proposed Ontology

2.3.1 The Set of Basic Objects: The Foundational Structure of Physical Reality

Hierarchical analysis of objects leads to the following implication.

If at each level of organization objects are structures formed from objects of the preceding level and can exist only in an environment formed by other objects, then this hierarchy cannot end with emptiness, since emptiness is not a set of objects and is incapable either of forming the structure of the objects themselves or of performing the function of a physical environment.

Accordingly, the lowest level of the hierarchy must correspond to a base set of objects. Basic objects are likewise organized entities that realize processes and states of existence and are themselves created by their own set, but they are no longer formed from objects of a lower level.

Within the proposed approach, it is precisely this set of basic objects that constitutes the foundational level of physical reality. What modern physics describes as the physical vacuum may be regarded as one of the states or regimes of this base set, rather than as a separate substance or abstract emptiness.

Material bodies and other physical structures are likewise not entities separate from the foundational level. Particles, atoms, bodies, and other localized physical structures are regarded as configurations, states, and processes of interaction of basic objects.

Fields are in turn interpreted as structures, processes of interaction, and coordinated changes in the states of objects of the respective levels.

Thus, within this ontology, the states of the physical vacuum, fields, and material entities are interpreted as different configurations of one and the same foundational structure of physical reality, formed by the set of basic objects.

2.3.2 Motion as a Wave Process of Transferring Structures

Another implication of the proposed ontology of objects is the interpretation of the concept of motion in its most general sense.

Since objects are structures that undergo a sequence of emergence, existence, and creation of new objects by the set, motion in the fundamental sense should be understood as the process of transferring these structures and creating new instances of them, realized through changes in their states.

The transfer of an object's structure cannot take place as an instantaneous displacement of a ready-made structure. It is realized as a sequence of coordinated state changes within which the structure is preserved, re-created, and transmitted between interacting objects and structures.

The need to preserve the structure during its transfer leads to the repetition and coordination of changes. In this sense, motion has a wave character as a form of preservation, transmission, and transfer of structure.

An important particular case is the mechanical motion of a body in classical and relativistic mechanics, which is usually considered as the change of the position of a material point in geometric space. Within the proposed approach, such motion can be reinterpreted as a wave process of transferring the structure of the body in a multilevel description of objects and their interactions.

In this sense, an object does not merely "move" through space, but exists through the process of motion, which ensures the preservation, transfer, and re-creation of its structure.

The implications of this approach will be considered in the next section.

3 Wave Approach to the Description of the Motion of Light and Massive Bodies

In the previous section it was shown that motion, in the fundamental sense, appears as a process of preservation and transfer of the structure of objects and is connected with the sequence of emergence, existence, creation of new objects by the set, and termination of existence of objects.

In the present section it is considered how such an approach may be applied to the description of the motion of light and of

massive bodies. In the case of light, the wave character of motion follows directly from electrodynamics. For massive bodies, classical and relativistic mechanics ordinarily describes motion as the change of position of a material point in space-time, although in quantum mechanics the motion of particles also admits a wave description.

In what follows the wave approach is used not for an analysis of the quantum-mechanical properties of particles, but as a general model of the phase description of processes of motion and transfer of structure consistent with the ontology of sets of objects.

The subsequent treatment is directed at the construction of a common wave phase description both for light and for the motion of massive bodies, and at the analysis of its consistency with the spacetime formalism of special relativity.

Methodologically the present section employs the approach according to which one and the same physical process may admit different but equivalent ways of description. The subsequent treatment is therefore built as a transition from experimentally established physical facts and existing physical formalisms to a more general wave phase description and to an analysis of its consequences. The treatment proposed here does not claim a revision of the standard physical theories; it provides for them a broader interpretive framework following from the ontology of sets of objects and does not alter the structure of the results already established.

3.1 Wave Description of Light and of Electromagnetic Processes

In modern physics light and electromagnetic processes are described as wave processes propagating in vacuum with the fundamental speed c . This description follows directly from the Maxwell equations of the electromagnetic field (Maxwell 1873; Landau and Lifshitz 1975).

3.1.1 From Classical Electrodynamics to an Abstract Phase Description

Background: classical electrodynamics and experiment.

From the Maxwell equations in vacuum, for one component of the electric field one has

$$\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad (1)$$

with

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varepsilon_0 \mu_0}}.$$

One of the solutions of this equation is a plane electromagnetic wave

$$E(x, t) = E_0 \cos(\omega t - kx) \quad (2)$$

with phase

$$\phi = \omega t - kx \quad (3)$$

and the relation

$$\frac{\omega}{k} = c. \quad (4)$$

A plane wave is the simplest mathematical solution of the wave equation, but it is not a localised physical structure.

Localised wave packets. In real physical processes electromagnetic radiation is normally described by localised wave packets. One of the simplest examples is the Gaussian wave packet

$$\begin{aligned} E(x, t) &= A \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \omega t/k)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cos(\omega t - kx) \\ &= A \exp\left(-\frac{(\omega t - kx)^2}{2(k\sigma)^2}\right) \cos(\omega t - kx). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In the second, equivalent form both the envelope and the harmonic carrier are functions of the same phase $\phi = \omega t - kx$; the parameter $k\sigma$ sets the width of the packet's localisation in units of phase.

Within the present work a localised electromagnetic wave packet is taken as a model of the photon. Such a model does not claim a description of the quantum properties of the photon and does not use the formalism of quantum field theory. For the

purposes of the present work it is sufficient to regard the photon as a localised massless wave structure that transfers its configuration in the process of propagation. It is in this sense that the term "photon" is used in what follows.

Transition to an abstract phase description. For the subsequent analysis we are interested not in the concrete form of a wave packet but in its phase structure. We shall therefore treat the wave process in terms of the abstract phase description

$$\phi_l = \Omega_l \tau - K_l \sigma. \quad (6)$$

Here the parameters τ and σ are not identified directly with physical time and space. The parameter τ characterises the sequence of changes of the configuration of the wave process, whereas the parameter σ characterises the propagation or transfer of that configuration. Accordingly, the parameters Ω_l and K_l characterise the intensity of these processes of change and of propagation.

In this way the phase description is built without any prior introduction of spatial and temporal coordinates and relies only on the internal structure of the wave process itself.

In addition we introduce the parameter

$$\Lambda_l := \frac{\Omega_l}{K_l}, \quad (7)$$

which characterises the ratio between the process of change of configuration and the process of its propagation. In the coordinate description of an electromagnetic wave this ratio corresponds to the quantity

$$\frac{\omega}{k} = c,$$

that is, to the phase velocity of a plane electromagnetic wave (4).

For a photon, therefore, the quantity Λ_l is a constant invariant structural characteristic of the wave process. In what follows we shall require that the value of Λ_l remains unchanged in all admissible frames of one and the same photon.

3.1.2 The Set of Frames of a Photon

Within the proposed ontology a physical process is regarded as primary physical reality, while its mathematical description is

secondary. One and the same photon may be represented in different ways without any change of its physical content.

Consider a localised electromagnetic wave packet (a photon), described by the phase function (6)

$$\phi_l = \Omega_l \tau - K_l \sigma$$

and by the structural characteristic (7)

$$\Lambda_l = \frac{\Omega_l}{K_l}.$$

The photon as a physical process does not depend on the way it is described. The different frames of one and the same photon must therefore correspond to one and the same phase structure and must preserve the value of the parameter Λ_l .

For every admissible frame q_l we introduce the transformation

$$S_l(q_l): (\tau, \sigma, \Omega_l, K_l) \mapsto (\tau', \sigma', \Omega'_l, K'_l), \quad (8)$$

satisfying the conditions

$$\phi'_l = \phi_l, \quad (9)$$

and

$$\frac{\Omega'_l}{K'_l} = \frac{\Omega_l}{K_l} = \Lambda_l. \quad (10)$$

The first condition expresses the invariance of the phase structure of the photon; the second, the preservation of its structural characteristic.

From these requirements there follows directly the wave invariant of the photon

$$\Omega_l^2 - \Lambda_l^2 K_l^2 = 0, \quad (11)$$

or, equivalently, in linear form

$$\Omega_l - \Lambda_l K_l = 0. \quad (12)$$

The substitution $\Lambda_l = c$ recovers the usual dispersion relation of an electromagnetic wave (4).

The set of all such admissible transformations constitutes the class of frames of the photon $S_l(q_l)$. The physical process thus remains unchanged, while its parameterisation may vary.

The structure of the transformations and the connection with special relativity. To determine the structure of the set $S_l(q_l)$ we consider the transformation between two admissible frames of a photon. The requirements of phase invariance (9) and of invariance of the structural characteristic (10) uniquely determine the class of admissible transformations

$$\sigma' = \Gamma (\sigma - q_l \tau), \quad \tau' = \Gamma \left(\tau - \frac{q_l}{\Lambda_l^2} \sigma \right), \quad (13)$$

with

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - q_l^2/\Lambda_l^2}}. \quad (14)$$

In this way the set of admissible frames of the photon constitutes a single consistent structure of transformations that preserves both the phase structure of the wave process and its structural characteristic Λ_l .

From the transformations indicated above there follows directly an invariant quadratic form

$$\Lambda_l^2 d\tau^2 - d\sigma^2 = \text{inv.} \quad (15)$$

If one applies the coordinate interpretation

$$\tau \rightarrow t, \quad \sigma \rightarrow x, \quad \Lambda_l = c,$$

the transformations obtained go over into the standard Lorentz transformations (Lorentz 1904; Einstein 1905) and the wave invariant takes the form of the Minkowski interval (Minkowski 1909)

$$c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 = \text{inv.} \quad (16)$$

Thus the set of admissible frames of one and the same photon has a structure equivalent to that of Minkowski spacetime.

3.2 Wave Description of the Motion of Massive Bodies

In the previous subsection it was shown that the wave description of light leads naturally to a phase invariant and to a set of admissible frames of the photon. We shall now consider whether an analogous approach may be applied to the motion of massive bodies.

Within the proposed ontology motion is not regarded as the displacement of a material point in a pre-given geometric space. On the contrary, motion is interpreted as a process of preservation, re-creation and transfer of the structure of a physical object. The geometric description records only the external result of this process, but not its internal physical content.

3.2.1 From Classical Mechanics to an Abstract Phase Description

Background: classical mechanics and experiment. By Newton's first law (Newton 1687; Landau and Lifshitz 1976) there exists a set of inertial frames of reference in which a free body is either at rest or in uniform rectilinear motion. In such motion the structure of the object is preserved unchanged, and the motion itself may be interpreted as a process of stable transfer of that structure.

Mathematically this corresponds to the Galilean transformation

$$x' = x - vt. \quad (17)$$

For a harmonic process the phase function

$$\phi = \omega t - kx$$

preserves its functional form under such a transformation, only the parameters ω and k being changed. For an arbitrary process the analogous result follows from the spectral decomposition into harmonic components.

This allows one to pass from the coordinate description of motion to its wave representation and to regard the motion of a massive body as a wave process of transfer of structure.

Within the proposed ontology the transfer of structure is regarded as a process that admits a phase description, by analogy with wave processes in physics. The motion of a massive object may therefore be represented through the evolution of the corresponding phase structure.

Transition to an abstract phase description. For the subsequent analysis we are interested not in the concrete form of a wave process but in its phase structure.

Unlike the massless case, for a massive object there exists a distinguished frame in which the object is at rest. In that frame the wave process is not associated with the transfer of structure, but characterises only its internal dynamics.

By analogy with the case of light we introduce the abstract phase description

$$\phi_m = \Omega_m \tau - K_m \sigma. \quad (18)$$

Here the parameter τ characterises the sequence of changes of the configuration of the wave process, while the parameter σ characterises the transfer or propagation of that configuration. The parameters Ω_m and K_m characterise, respectively, the intensity of the internal dynamics and the intensity of the transfer of structure.

In the rest state of a massive object there is a frame for which

$$K_{m,0} = 0, \quad (19)$$

and the phase function takes the form

$$\phi_{m,0} = \Omega_{m,0} \tau. \quad (20)$$

Unlike the photon, therefore, a massive object admits a distinguished frame corresponding to the internal equilibrium of the wave process.

3.2.2 The Set of Frames of a Massive Object

Within the proposed ontology a physical process is regarded as primary physical reality, while its mathematical description is secondary. One and the same massive object may be represented in different ways without any change of its physical content.

Consider a massive object described by the phase function (18)

$$\phi_m = \Omega_m \tau - K_m \sigma$$

with the distinguished rest frame (19)-(20), in which $K_{m,0} = 0$ and the phase function takes the form $\phi_{m,0} = \Omega_{m,0} \tau$.

A massive object as a physical process does not depend on the way it is described. The different frames of one and the same object must therefore correspond to one and the same phase structure and must preserve those characteristics that belong to the object itself rather than to a particular frame.

For every admissible frame q_m we introduce the transformation

$$S_m(q_m): (\tau, \sigma, \Omega_m, K_m) \mapsto (\tau', \sigma', \Omega'_m, K'_m), \quad (21)$$

which satisfies the requirement of phase invariance

$$\phi'_m = \phi_m \quad (22)$$

together with a structural condition of linearity in the parameter q_m .

The general class of transformations. In the class of linear transformations of the parameters (τ, σ) the most general one-parameter family preserving the phase (22) and containing the identity transformation at $q_m = 0$ takes the form

$$\sigma' = \Gamma (\sigma - q_m \tau), \quad \tau' = \Gamma \left(\tau - \frac{q_m}{\Lambda_m^2} \sigma \right), \quad (23)$$

with

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - q_m^2 / \Lambda_m^2}}. \quad (24)$$

In this family a structural constant Λ_m arises with the meaning of a velocity, which sets the scale relating the temporal and spatial parts of the phase description. The parameter q_m in this connection has the meaning of the relative velocity between two frames and is bounded by the condition $|q_m| < \Lambda_m$.

At this stage Λ_m is no more than a structural characteristic of the class of transformations. Its value is not determined by the requirements of phase invariance and of linearity alone.

Limiting cases. For $\Lambda_m \rightarrow \infty$ the transformations (23)-(24) go over into the Galilean ones,

$$\sigma' = \sigma - q_m \tau, \quad \tau' = \tau,$$

corresponding to the classical kinematic regime without any restriction on the relative velocity between frames. For a finite value of Λ_m the transformations have the structure of Lorentz transformations with structural velocity Λ_m , and the set of admissible frames forms a Lorentz-like family with parameter $q_m \in (-\Lambda_m, \Lambda_m)$.

The type of the structure thus obtained is determined by the value of Λ_m , but this value itself cannot be fixed within the construction of the set of frames of a single object.

The wave invariant. From the transformations (23)-(24), together with the requirement of phase invariance, there follows the existence of a constant combination of parameters

$$\Omega_m^2 - \Lambda_m^2 K_m^2 = \text{const.} \quad (25)$$

Computing this quantity in the proper frame of the object, for which $K_{m,0} = 0$, one obtains

$$\Omega_m^2 - \Lambda_m^2 K_m^2 = \Omega_{m,0}^2, \quad (26)$$

where $\Omega_{m,0}$ is the frequency of the object in its rest frame (20). This quantity depends solely on the internal properties of the object and does not change under transitions between frames.

Structurally, in contrast to the photonic case — where the vanishing of the wave invariant (11) expresses the constancy of the phase velocity $\Omega_l/K_l = \Lambda_l$ in all frames — for a massive object the constant value of $\Omega_{m,0}^2$ arises from the existence of a distinguished rest frame. Accordingly, Λ_m appears here as a structural constant of the class of transformations itself, and not as an invariant ratio of the parameters within a given frame.

From the transformations indicated above there follows directly an invariant quadratic form

$$\Lambda_m^2 d\tau^2 - d\sigma^2 = \text{inv}, \quad (27)$$

which in the Lorentz-like case takes the form of the Minkowski interval with structural velocity Λ_m .

It is worth noting that in the limit $\Omega_{m,0} \rightarrow 0$ the relation (26) formally takes the same structural form as the wave invariant of the photon (11), the structural velocities Λ_l and Λ_m entering symmetrically. This structural coincidence indicates the possibility of a single formalism for light and for massive bodies, but the ontological character of their relation is not determined at the level of the set of frames $S_m(q_m)$ itself and is considered in the next subsection.

The set of all admissible transformations forms the class of frames of a massive object $S_m(q_m)$.

At this stage the sets of frames $S_l(q_l)$ and $S_m(q_m)$ have been constructed independently of one another; furthermore, for the massive object the structural constant Λ_m has not yet received a physical value, and the type of the structure obtained (Galilean

or Lorentz-like) is not determined within the construction of a single object. The question of the relation between these two constructions and of the physical meaning of Λ_m is taken up in the next subsection through an analysis of the interaction of light and massive objects.

3.3 Unification of the Frames of Light and of Massive Bodies

In subsections 3.1 and 3.2 the sets of admissible frames of the photon $S_l(q_l)$ and of the massive object $S_m(q_m)$ were constructed independently of one another. In both cases the initial requirement was the invariance of the phase structure of the physical process.

For the photon there was, in addition, the requirement of invariance of the ratio (7), $\Lambda_l = \Omega_l/K_l$, which means the constancy of the phase velocity in all admissible frames of one and the same light process.

Consider now physical processes in which light and massive objects participate jointly: emission, absorption, scattering, and so on. Such processes are single physical processes and do not admit different frames for their constituents.

An admissible frame of a massive object must therefore at the same time be an admissible frame of the photon participating in the same process, and conversely. Hence one identifies the parameters of the frames

$$q_l = q_m \equiv q, \quad (28)$$

and the structural velocities

$$\Lambda_l = \Lambda_m \equiv \Lambda. \quad (29)$$

The identification of the sets $S_l(q)$ and $S_m(q)$ means that what is shared between the two constructions are precisely the *frame coordinates* (τ, σ) and the *structural velocity* Λ — quantities that belong not to individual objects but to the set of admissible frames of physical processes itself. After unification, light and massive objects are considered in one frame (τ, σ) with a common structural velocity Λ .

At the same time, the wave parameters of the photon (Ω_l, K_l) and of the massive object (Ω_m, K_m) characterise no longer the

frame but the specific physical process and remain *distinct* quantities; the unification of frames does not identify them with one another.

In the common set of frames the photon satisfies the relation

$$\Omega_l^2 - \Lambda^2 K_l^2 = 0, \quad (30)$$

whereas for the massive object

$$\Omega_m^2 - \Lambda^2 K_m^2 = \Omega_0^2, \quad (31)$$

where Ω_0 is the proper rest frequency of the massive object (the quantity denoted in §3.2 by $\Omega_{m,0}$). No common “unified” invariant is introduced here for the photon and the massive object: they are described by two distinct relations (30) and (31) within one and the same frame.

Thus light and massive objects belong to a single kinematic frame structure and differ by their wave parameters and by the value of the wave invariant.

3.4 Factorisation of the Wave Invariant and the Light-Like Components

The wave invariant of a massive object (31) in the coordinate interpretation $\Lambda \rightarrow c$ takes the form

$$\Omega_m^2 - c^2 K_m^2 = \Omega_0^2. \quad (32)$$

The algebraic identity $a^2 - b^2 = (a+b)(a-b)$ with $a = \Omega_m$ and $b = cK_m$ gives

$$(\Omega_m + cK_m)(\Omega_m - cK_m) = \Omega_0^2. \quad (33)$$

The factorisation (33) is itself pure algebra; what is non-trivial is how the pairs $(\Omega_m \pm cK_m)$ behave under the transition between frames. Set

$$Q_{m,+} := \Omega_m + cK_m, \quad Q_{m,-} := \Omega_m - cK_m. \quad (34)$$

Boost and rescaling of $Q_{m,\pm}$. For the standard Lorentz boost along the axis σ (respectively x after the coordinate interpretation) with velocity v the wave parameters of a massive object

transform as

$$\Omega'_m = \gamma(\Omega_m - vK_m), \quad K'_m = \gamma\left(K_m - \frac{v}{c^2}\Omega_m\right), \quad \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}. \quad (35)$$

Substitution of (35) into the definitions (34) gives

$$\Omega'_m + cK'_m = \gamma\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)(\Omega_m + cK_m), \quad \Omega'_m - cK'_m = \gamma\left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)(\Omega_m - cK_m). \quad (36)$$

Introduce the positive parameter

$$q := \gamma\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{1 - v/c}{1 + v/c}}, \quad (37)$$

so that $\gamma(1 + v/c) = 1/q$, whereupon (36) yields

$$Q'_{m,+} = q Q_{m,+}, \quad Q'_{m,-} = \frac{1}{q} Q_{m,-}, \quad (38)$$

where $Q'_{m,\pm}$ are the same combinations built from (Ω'_m, K'_m) . The product of components is preserved:

$$Q'_{m,+} \cdot Q'_{m,-} = Q_{m,+} \cdot Q_{m,-} = \Omega_0^2, \quad (39)$$

which recovers directly the factorised wave invariant (33).

The parameter q as a Doppler factor. The parameter q in (37) coincides with the well-known relativistic Doppler factor. If one introduces the velocity via the rapidity θ by $v/c = \tanh \theta$, then

$$q = e^{-\theta}, \quad 1/q = e^{\theta},$$

and the rescaling law (38) becomes exponential in the rapidity. Under the composition of two successive boosts the rapidities add, while the rescaling factors of $Q_{m,\pm}$ multiply — a structure characteristic of the one-dimensional Lorentz group.

Geometric meaning of $Q_{m,\pm}$: light-like coordinates. The transformations (38) show that $Q_{m,\pm}$ are the eigen-coordinates of the boost: each of them under the transformation (35) is only multiplied by a scalar, without mixing with the other. In the space of parameters (Ω_m, K_m) this corresponds to the directions

$$\Omega_m = \pm cK_m, \quad (40)$$

i.e. to the two generators of the light cone. In the coordinates $(Q_{m,+}, Q_{m,-})$ the wave invariant (33) appears as the equation of a hyperbola $Q_{m,+} Q_{m,-} = \text{const}$, invariant under the transformations $Q_{m,\pm} \mapsto \lambda^{\pm 1} Q_{m,\pm}$ with $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+$. The boosts (35) are precisely such transformations with $\lambda = q^{-1}$.

The photon in the coordinates $Q_{l,\pm}$. For a photon the wave invariant (30) in the coordinate interpretation $\Lambda \rightarrow c$ takes the form

$$\Omega_l^2 - c^2 K_l^2 = 0.$$

Introducing the analogues of (34),

$$Q_{l,+} := \Omega_l + cK_l, \quad Q_{l,-} := \Omega_l - cK_l,$$

one obtains

$$Q_{l,+} Q_{l,-} = 0,$$

that is, one of the components necessarily vanishes:

- for propagation in the positive direction of σ , where $\Omega_l = +cK_l$, one has $Q_{l,-} = 0$ and $Q_{l,+} = 2\Omega_l = 2cK_l$;
- for propagation in the negative direction, where $\Omega_l = -cK_l$, one has $Q_{l,+} = 0$ and $Q_{l,-} = 2\Omega_l$.

Thus the photon in the coordinates $Q_{l,\pm}$ is described by a single non-vanishing light-like component and corresponds to motion along one of the generators of the light cone.

Light-like components of the massive process. Comparison of the photon relation $Q_{l,+} Q_{l,-} = 0$ with the massive one,

$$Q_{m,+} Q_{m,-} = \Omega_0^2,$$

shows that the quantities $Q_{m,+}$ and $Q_{m,-}$ belong to the same light-like directions $\Omega = \pm cK$ as the photon processes. For the photon only one of these two components is present; for the massive process both are present simultaneously.

The parameters of the massive process are uniquely recovered from $Q_{m,\pm}$:

$$\Omega_m = \frac{Q_{m,+} + Q_{m,-}}{2}, \quad K_m = \frac{Q_{m,+} - Q_{m,-}}{2c}. \quad (41)$$

Hence the quantities (Ω_m, K_m) may be regarded as derived from the two light-like components $Q_{m,+}$ and $Q_{m,-}$ that belong to the same kinematic structure in which photon processes are described.

In the proper frame of the massive object $K_m = 0$, so that

$$Q_{m,+} = Q_{m,-} = \Omega_0,$$

i.e. the state of rest corresponds to the symmetric state of the two light-like components. Under a transition to another frame this symmetry is broken:

$$Q'_{m,+} = q Q_{m,+}, \quad Q'_{m,-} = q^{-1} Q_{m,-},$$

but their product remains unchanged:

$$Q'_{m,+} Q'_{m,-} = Q_{m,+} Q_{m,-} = \Omega_0^2.$$

Interpretation of the parameters of the massive process.

The factorisation of the wave invariant singles out two quantities $Q_{m,+}$ and $Q_{m,-}$ belonging to the light-like directions $\Omega = \pm cK$. Within the proposed wave description these quantities may be interpreted as the parameters of two oppositely directed light-like components of the massive process. Denoting the proper frequencies of these components by $\Omega_{l,+}$ and $\Omega_{l,-}$ and setting

$$Q_{m,+} = 2\Omega_{l,+}, \quad Q_{m,-} = 2\Omega_{l,-}, \quad (42)$$

one obtains directly from the definitions (34)

$$\Omega_m = \Omega_{l,+} + \Omega_{l,-}, \quad K_m = \frac{\Omega_{l,+} - \Omega_{l,-}}{c}. \quad (43)$$

The relation (43) is the principal content of the factorisation: the parameters (Ω_m, K_m) of the massive process are not independent quantities but are expressed through two oppositely directed light-like components — Ω_m as their sum of frequencies, cK_m as the measure of the asymmetry between them. In the proper frame ($K_m = 0$) one has $\Omega_{l,+} = \Omega_{l,-} = \Omega_0/2$ — the state of rest corresponds to the symmetric state of the two light-like components.

The algebraic subscript m on $Q_{m,\pm}$, required for the link with the factorisation of the massive invariant, becomes superfluous at the interpretive level: $Q_{m,+}$ and $Q_{m,-}$ are light-like quantities of

the same kind as the photonic $Q_{l,\pm}$ and do not themselves carry any property of being “massive”. In this reading the massive process appears not as a distinct ontological category but as a composition of two oppositely directed light-like processes; the parameters (Ω_m, K_m) turn out to be derived from these components. In what follows we shall use the notation

$$Q_{\pm} := Q_{m,\pm} = 2\Omega_{l,\pm}. \quad (44)$$

Natural scale of the light-like components. The interpretation of Q_{\pm} as two light-like components of one process makes natural the choice of the scale of these components themselves. For the photon the relations $Q_{l,+} = 2\Omega_l$, $Q_{l,-} = 0$ (or vice versa) show that the scale is set by the light-like process itself — by the value of its single non-vanishing component. For the massive process, interpreted as a composition of two such components, the natural continuation of this logic is the parameterisation

$$Q_+ = q, \quad Q_- = q^{-1},$$

in which the invariant takes the normalised form

$$Q_+ Q_- = 1. \quad (45)$$

The state of rest corresponds to the symmetric value $Q_+ = Q_- = 1$, while motion corresponds to the breaking of this symmetry by mutually inverse rescaling of the components.

The transition from $Q_+ Q_- = \Omega_0^2$ to (45) is not an external normalisation condition but an expression of the fact that both components Q_{\pm} belong to one and the same light-like structure, in which the scale is set by the process itself. It does not touch either the structure of spacetime or the fundamental role of c , which remains in the very definition $Q_{\pm} = \Omega \pm cK$, in the wave invariant $\Omega^2 - c^2 K^2$ and in the Doppler factor $q = \sqrt{(1 - v/c)/(1 + v/c)}$. In this reading Ω_0 appears not as an independent fundamental quantity but as a scale parameter: the value taken by the symmetric components in the state of rest, while all physically significant information about motion is contained in the asymmetry between the light-like components and is described by the parameter q .

3.5 Further Consequences of This Interpretation

The proposed interpretation — the photon as a wave process with a single light-like component and the massive process as a wave process with two simultaneously present light-like components — leads to a number of consequences which concern both the individuality of a single photon and the structure of space-time. We register them here in the form of preliminary formulations; their systematic consideration is a matter for further work.

A single photon in different frames: the absence of an invariant frequency. The set of admissible frames $S(q)$, restricted to the light cone $\Omega_l = \pm \Lambda K_l$, contains frames in which the photon has an arbitrary positive frequency: for every value $\Omega_l > 0$ there exists a frame in which the photon under consideration has precisely that frequency. In particular, in one frame “red” and “blue” photons may be represented as “green” photons in correspondingly chosen other frames. In this sense the notion of the frequency of a photon is not invariant and cannot serve as a mark of the individuality of a single photon.

Several photons and the phase as a mark of distinction. Let us now turn to several photons in one fixed frame. They differ from one another in their phase functions $\phi_l(\tau, \sigma) = \Omega_l \tau - K_l \sigma$, with their values of (Ω_l, K_l) lying on the light cone. Under a change of frame these functions are transformed jointly, but the *difference between the phase functions at each event* (τ, σ) is preserved in a structurally invariant way. This suggests the formulation: the individuality of a photon in the present scheme is given not by the value of its frequency but by its *phase relation* to other wave processes. The present formalism is compatible with an interpretation in which the various manifestations of photons are regarded as states of one and the same wave process, differing only in their phase; a more detailed analysis of this reading lies beyond the scope of the present paper.

Velocity as a Doppler asymmetry between light-like components. In the proposed reading the relative velocity of a massive process acquires a direct physical meaning. The symmetric

state $Q_+ = Q_- = 1$ (equivalently $\Omega_{l,+} = \Omega_{l,-} = \Omega_0/2$) is the state of rest: the two light-like components are kinematically indistinguishable. A non-vanishing relative velocity v in an external frame manifests itself as a mutually opposite relativistic Doppler shift of these components,

$$\Omega_{l,+} \mapsto q \Omega_{l,+}, \quad \Omega_{l,-} \mapsto q^{-1} \Omega_{l,-}, \quad q = \sqrt{\frac{1 - v/c}{1 + v/c}}.$$

The relative velocity between a massive process and a given frame is therefore not a primary kinematic property of the process itself: it is the Doppler asymmetry between its two light-like components in that frame. The Lorentz transformation between two frames reduces to the mutually inverse Doppler rescaling of these components.

Acceleration in such a picture is the transition from one proper frame to another. In every proper frame the internal structure is again symmetric ($Q_+ = Q_-$), but the transition itself means a change of the phase of the light-like process, common to both counter-propagating components. States of uniform motion are therefore structurally equivalent: they differ not by an internal asymmetry but by the phase of the light-like process.

In this sense mass may be interpreted as a measure of the phase rearrangement required for the transition between different states of motion of a massive process. Uniform motion does not require such a rearrangement and therefore does not exhibit mass directly. Mass acquires its physical content only under acceleration, when in order to pass to a new state of motion the phase state of the light-like components of the process must be changed.

Phase difference as the additive parameter of the set of frames. The notions of a phase relation introduced in the preceding paragraphs admit a precise formulation in terms of the phase difference between frames. For two frames $S(q_i)$ and $S(q_j)$ of one and the same wave process we define their *phase difference* (or the rapidity of the transition $j \rightarrow i$) as

$$\Delta\theta_{ij} := \theta_i - \theta_j = -\ln(q_i/q_j), \quad (46)$$

where $\theta_k = -\ln q_k$ is the rapidity of the k -th frame. From (46) there follow directly:

- antisymmetry: $\Delta\theta_{ji} = -\Delta\theta_{ij}$;
- additivity (the cocycle condition): $\Delta\theta_{ij} + \Delta\theta_{jk} = \Delta\theta_{ik}$;
- group structure: the set of values of $\Delta\theta$ forms the abelian group $(\mathbb{R}, +)$ under the composition of boosts.

If v_{ij} is the relative velocity between the frames i and j , then

$$\Delta\theta_{ij} = \text{artanh}(v_{ij}/c), \quad (47)$$

and the non-linear relativistic velocity-addition law $v_{ik} = (v_{ij} + v_{jk})/(1 + v_{ij}v_{jk}/c^2)$ is the projection of the trivial additive structure (46) through the hyperbolic tangent. For a massive object the rapidity of the frame j is expressible through its light-like components Q_{\pm} :

$$\theta_j = \frac{1}{2} \ln(Q_-^{(j)}/Q_+^{(j)}), \quad (48)$$

that is, the rapidity is a logarithmic measure of the asymmetry between the light-like components of the process in the given frame.

In this language velocity, rapidity and the phase difference between frames become three forms of one additive quantity: $\Delta\theta_{ij}$ is at once (i) the group parameter of the boosts between frames, (ii) a geometric characteristic of the relative motion, computable as artanh of the velocity, and (iii) a measure of the phase asymmetry between Q_{\pm} accumulated in the transition from one frame to another. The set $S(q)$ appears as a one-dimensional phase space with a natural group structure in which the composition of transitions between frames is reduced to the addition of phase differences.

Phase as the unifying principle of kinematics. The notions of inertial frame, Doppler shift, relative velocity and acceleration appear in the proposed reading as different manifestations of one and the same structure — phase relations between light-like processes:

- an inertial frame $S(q)$ is a phase state, parameterised by the rapidity $\theta = -\ln q$;
- the Doppler shift of a photon is a phase shift of its single light-like component between two frames;

- the relative velocity of a massive process is the Doppler asymmetry between its two light-like components in a given frame;
- acceleration is a change of the phase of the light-like process, common to both components.

In this sense the entire kinematics of special relativity reduces to the calculus of phase relations between light-like processes; mass and motion acquire physical content only through these relations.

Spacetime as the frame structure of a single process. In this reading the spacetime of any object — of a photon as well as of a massive one — is formed by its own wave process and possesses the same structure of the set of frames $S(q)$, invariant under Lorentz-like transformations. In this sense spacetime is not an external stage on which objects move; it is the structure of the set of frames of the wave process itself.

The observable differences between physical processes do not belong to the processes themselves taken in isolation. The frequency of a photon, the relative velocity of a massive object, and other kinematic characteristics acquire content only through the correlation of different wave processes. Within the proposed construction such differences appear as phase relations between the light-like components of the processes.

In particular, the relative velocity of a massive process may be interpreted as the phase asymmetry between its two light-like components, while the frequency of a photon is determined by the phase state of its single light-like component. The difference between relative velocities v_1 and v_2 , as well as the difference between the frequencies of photons, appears thus not through a change of the internal structure of the process, but through the difference of its phase state with respect to other processes.

Such an interpretation calls for further analysis and study.

4 Ontological Properties of the Set of Basic Objects

In classical mechanics (Landau and Lifshitz 1976), a mechanical system appears as a configuration, and a change of configuration, of material points in space. The material points play the role of basic objects of the description, and on top of this the postulates of homogeneity and isotropy of space, together with the homogeneity of time, are introduced. From these symmetries the fundamental conservation laws — of energy, momentum and angular momentum — subsequently follow.

If, however, a mechanical system is considered in empty space, the postulated properties of space and time do not receive any concrete physical realisation: there is no structure that actually instantiates homogeneity, isotropy, or the homogeneity of absolute time. Space and time remain a priori background entities, posited by requirement.

In the ontology proposed in the present work no such a priori background is introduced. Space is regarded as a set of basic objects, which by their very definition are processes and may occupy different states. Within such a description the postulated properties of space and time receive a concrete ontological realisation:

- **Homogeneity of space** is secured by the structural identity of the basic objects: no region of space is singled out, since all objects filling it have the same internal organisation.
- **Isotropy of space** is secured by the fact that the characteristic scale of the basic objects is significantly smaller than that of the known physical objects. On the scale of the latter no direction is singled out, since averaging over a large number of equivalent basic objects restores the spatial symmetry.
- **Homogeneity of time** is secured by the fact that each basic object repeats one and the same internal process of change of states. No moment of time is singled out relative to the others.

- **Locality** is realised through the possibility of singling out a subset of basic objects that constitutes a localised structure of a higher level of organisation.
- **Globality** is realised through the structural identity of the basic objects throughout the whole set: any local phenomenon may be carried over to any other point of space without change of structure.

In what follows these properties are extended to an interpretation of the statistical and field-theoretic characteristics of the set of basic objects.

4.1 Entropy of the Basic State and Structured States

In statistical physics entropy is associated with the number of microstates compatible with given macroscopic conditions (Boltzmann 1877; Landau and Lifshitz 1980): $S \sim \ln \Omega$, where Ω denotes the number of accessible microconfigurations. Within the proposed ontology this definition is applied to the set of basic objects itself.

In the basic state all objects are structurally equivalent, no configuration is singled out, and the changes of their internal states are statistically independent. Under such conditions the number of admissible microconfigurations of the medium is maximal, Ω_{base} , and the basic state is characterised by maximal entropy. Unlike the standard treatment of the vacuum as the “absence of objects” with zero entropy, here entropy belongs to the set of basic objects itself and reflects its statistical capacity.

The appearance of a localised structure of a higher level of organisation corresponds to the emergence of correlations between the states of a subset of basic objects. The number of admissible microconfigurations in that subset decreases,

$$\Omega_{\text{local}} < \Omega_{\text{base}}, \quad \Delta S < 0, \quad (49)$$

which corresponds to a local decrease of entropy relative to the basic state. This does not contradict the second law of thermodynamics, since the region in question is open with respect to the

remainder of the space of objects: the local decrease is compensated by a corresponding increase of entropy in the surrounding medium, and the global entropy does not decrease.

4.2 The Transition Region, Fields and Interaction

Between a localised structure and the distant basic medium a transition region arises, in which the degree of correlation of states changes with distance. This produces a spatial entropy gradient,

$$S = S(\mathbf{r}), \quad \nabla S(\mathbf{r}) \neq 0. \quad (50)$$

The transition region is not a separate ontological entity; it reflects the gradual matching of the local ordered state with the global basic state.

Within this description a physical field appears naturally not as an autonomous entity but as a characteristic of the spatial distribution of the entropy of the medium induced by a localised structure. The field strengths correspond to the degree of deviation of the state of the medium from the basic state and to the rate of its relaxation. Different types of fields (electromagnetic, gravitational and others) correspond to different ways in which structures at the basic level influence the entropy distribution of the surrounding medium.

If another localised object is present in the vicinity, the transition regions overlap and the spatial distribution of entropy becomes asymmetric. Along the line connecting the objects the contributions to the entropy distribution may reinforce or weaken one another, which leads to a directed interaction between the objects. The character of this interaction is determined by the properties of the structures themselves and by the way in which the entropy distribution is realised in the medium. In this interpretation entropy figures as a characteristic of the state of the medium, while the interaction itself is realised through its field-like state.

4.3 Preservation of Localised Structures in a Medium with Maximal Entropy

In the section devoted to the ontology of objects, the principle was introduced according to which physical objects exist not as solitary formations but as sets of realisations of a certain type. The preservation of such an object in time is possible only on the condition that the set continually creates new realisations of the same type. This statement has a general character and is not tied to any concrete physical mechanism.

The treatment of the entropic characteristics of localised structures shows that any single structure of this kind is thermodynamically unstable. The local decrease of entropy needed to sustain an ordered state is inevitably accompanied by a tendency to relaxation and decay, in accordance with the second law of thermodynamics. In a medium with maximal entropy a long-lasting static existence of a single localised structure is impossible.

It follows that the existence of an object as an ontological entity cannot rest on the stability of a single realisation. Individual localised structures may emerge and disappear as a result of fluctuations and relaxation processes, while the preservation of the object in time is secured by the multiplicity of such realisations.

4.4 Information Capacity of Space

As shown above, the basic state has maximal entropy, corresponding to the maximal number of accessible microstates. In information theory (Shannon 1948) entropy determines the maximal capacity of a channel of information transmission: a channel with zero entropy is incapable of transmitting information, since it possesses no alternative states.

The Shannon formula for information entropy has the form

$$H = - \sum_i p_i \log_2 p_i, \quad (51)$$

where p_i is the probability of the i -th state of the system. Maximal entropy is attained when all states are equiprobable, which corresponds to the maximal information capacity of the medium.

If the basic state possesses a large number of admissible microstates, then space filled by the set of basic objects possesses

a non-zero and substantial information capacity. This makes it a natural medium for the propagation of structured processes and signals.

In this way, the properties that classical mechanics postulates of space and time as a priori structures arise in the proposed ontology as consequences of the structural organisation of the set of basic objects. The symmetries and conservation laws, the entropic characteristics of the state of the medium, the field-theoretic interpretation of interactions, and the stability of structures through the creation of new realisations by their set — all these characteristics receive a common ontological basis: they reflect the properties of the physical medium constituted by the set of basic objects, rather than those of an external geometric background.

5 Conclusion

This paper has developed an ontology based on sets of similar objects, in which an object appears not as a single isolated entity but as a class of realisations of a certain type that is continually created by the set itself. It has been shown that such an ontology is naturally consistent with the mathematical formalism of contemporary physics: the wave description of light and of massive bodies, together with the structure of Minkowski spacetime, follows from the requirement that the phase of one and the same physical process be invariant across the set of admissible frames, while the symmetries, conservation laws, fields and interactions of physics receive an ontological interpretation through the statistical and structural properties of the set of basic objects.

The wave treatment developed in this paper gives an ontological interpretation of the kinematics of special relativity. The motion of a massive body, like the propagation of a photon, appears as a wave process on the set of admissible frames; the requirement of phase invariance on this set leads to the structure of Minkowski spacetime and to Lorentz-like transformations between frames. The photon is described by a single light-like component, the massive process by two, and the relative velocity of a massive object acquires the meaning of a phase asymmetry between these components. Mass appears not as a characteristic

of uniform motion but as a measure of the phase rearrangement of the process at the transition between states of motion.

According to the criteria formulated in the paper, the following sets of objects can be distinguished:

- the set of basic objects, forming the physical medium;
- photons and other massless particles;
- electrons and other massive elementary particles;
- organic systems — DNA and proteins;
- organic cells;
- complete organisms.

For elementary particles the criterion of creation by the set on which the proposed ontology is built is satisfied in a natural way: the very motion of a particle can be regarded as the re-creation of its configuration through time. Atoms are stable quantum systems of elementary particles; their ontological status within the proposed ontology requires a separate determination. Molecular, crystalline and liquid states of matter are regarded not as separate sets of objects but as structures formed out of the objects of the preceding levels. Together with such structures, the listed sets of objects constitute the basis for the considerable variety of phenomena observed in the surrounding world.

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